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The Novel and Modernity

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***Abstract:** Modernity is one of the most important and relevant problems of fiction, especially prose. All researchers who talk about the problem of modernity are of the same opinion that modernity is based on real life, its artistic reflection and the image of modern man. A work of fiction that is not related to real life, its events and the lives of characters who are participants in these events cannot be considered a modern work.*

The manifestation of modernity in an artistic work is seen in the writer's system of images, typical events and full characters. If the writer recreates life in the work of art, if he is able to present the events he describes, human images at the level of artistic generalization, his work will resonate with the demands of modernity. In short, turning the truth of life into an artistic truth is one of the main conditions of modernity. It would be naive to think of modernity as only writing about modern life, reflecting today's events and today's people in literature. There are works whose theme is taken from historical events, but those works also reflect modern-sounding thoughts and ideas about our contemporary era. Don't we come across ideas that resonate with today in Nizami's "Khamsa", Sabir's "Hophopnama", J. Jabbarli's dramas, Javid's plays, and S.Vurgun's poetry? Therefore, it is necessary to look for the type of modernity in the artistic work itself.

Examples related to the explanation of the concept of modernity, its meaning and essence, the reflection of reality through artistic vision, the image of a modern hero, and other tasks are analyzed in the article.

***Key words:** fiction, prose, novel, modernity, historicity, thought, idea.*

INTRODUCTION

There are different opinions about the emergence, origin and stages of development of the novel in literary criticism. However, no matter how different these ideas are, there are some general considerations that it is more correct to refer to them first. It is assumed that the first examples of the novel, which is considered the largest form of the epic genre, appeared in ancient literature. Roman researchers mention the names of a number of large-scale works of art created in antiquity. These are "Daphnis and Chloe" by Long, "Satyricon" by Petroni, "The Golden Ass" by Apuleius and other works.

One of the most important factors for the development of the novel is the drastic changes in society and social life. At the same time, it was necessary for literature to break out of a certain narrow framework and enter a new stage of its development. Such a period in history was the Renaissance. This is a concept covering the 12th-15th centuries and the radical changes that took place in world culture, the new culture, art, literature, and science created on the basis of a new outlook. The Renaissance gave world literature great artists such as A.Dante, F.Petrarch, J.Boccaccio, F.Rabelais, M.Cervantes, W.Shakespeare. The rise of the Renaissance in the world culture was not a phenomenon specific to Europe or the West. For example, in China, the Renaissance manifested itself earlier. In Azerbaijan, the 12th century is considered the beginning of the renaissance period. In this century, a genius wordsmith such as Nizami Ganjavi grew up, his "Khamsa" is considered the peak of the Azerbaijani renaissance.

Thus, the period and circumstances were created for the formation of the novel genre, its sharp differentiation from the examples that arose in antiquity, and the flourishing of culture, literature and art also provided an incentive for the development of the genre.

The main part

The emergence of a new genre in world literature, of course, did not mean its complete formation and self-determination. The novel, like other genres, had to go from simple to complex. The novels such as "Gargantua and Pantagruel" by F. Rabelais, "Don Quixote" by M. Cervantes, etc. are considered the most perfect novels of the Renaissance. In particular, Cervantes' novel is considered one of the rare pearls of world literature. All scenes of the social life of that time were reflected here. Many qualities characteristic of the novel - strong characters, conflicts, artistic reflection of the truths of life - were brightly displayed in this work.

The novel belongs to the epic genre of literature, and the description of events in examples of the classical novel type, demonstration of human characters in the course of development are of the main conditions. That is why many researchers have called many poems written in verse, but having a certain plot line and describing life events and human characters in detail, as verse novels. In world literature, the novel experienced its brightest period in the 19th century. The history of the realist type novel also begins from this period. XIX century world literature includes V. Scott, C. Dickens (English), O. Balzac, E. Zola, G. Flaubert, V. Hugo, G. Maupassant (French), L. Tolstoy, I. Turgenev, F. Dostoevsky, It provided outstanding novelists such as I. Goncharov (Russian), R. Covanyoli (Italian). This tradition continued in the 20th century. R. Rolland, A. France, A. Barbus, H. Mann, T. Dreiser, M. Gorky, A. Tolstoy, M. Sholokhov, G. Marquez, W. Faulkner, J. Golsuorsi, E. Hemingway, J. Joyce, M. Proust, F. Kafka, M. Sholokhov, Ch. Aitmatov are considered masters of the novel art of the 20th century.

M. Bakhtin, an eminent literary critic and researcher of F. Dostoyevsky's legacy, writes in an article: "The novel is the only genre among all genres of prose that develops, improves, and enriches in the course of time. The genre that keeps pace with time and century is the novel. (2)

The novel acquired this authority by the breadth of its scope, literary and philosophical mission, and more active attitude to human problems. In the words of literary critic D. Grani: "The novel is the foundation of artistic prose. The novel is a platform where the most pressing problems of modernity can be solved." (3)

How did the novel become the number one literary genre? According to V.Q. Belinsky's phrase, "it killed everything, it swallowed everything", did it take control of the hearts of the readers? There are several reasons for this: firstly, people's consciousness, attitude to life, and their literary taste gradually developed. The reader wanted to understand the essence of events happening around him, interpersonal relations, events happening in society. Lyrics and poetry were not able to meet these requirements. Although the lyric expresses the deepest feelings of the human heart, it does not have the opportunity to reflect the important problems of life and reality. V.G. Belinsky wrote: "In our time, the novel and the short story have suppressed all other types of literature and put them in the background and have taken a dominant position in literature. What is this witch called novel? What is the reason for his fascination with the educated masses? What does he tell them about, what does he teach them, what does he attract them with? The content of the novel is an artistic analysis of modern society, revealing the invisible foundations of society that are kept hidden from the society itself by customary habits and thoughtlessness. The task of the modern novel is to reflect life in all its naked truth. Therefore, it is very natural that the novel, as an exception, attracted everyone's attention compared to all other types of literature: the society considers the novel as its mirror and looks at it and sees itself, understands itself." (1,220-221)

In our opinion, it cannot be overstated that the great influence of the novel and its superior position in the description of life events compared to other genres. It remains contemporary even today among the classical definitions given to the novel.

A second reason: the novel is a genre that reflects all the manifestations of social life. Life has dramatic, tragic and comic sides. The tragic fates of heroes are reflected in the tragedies of the great English playwright V. Shakespeare. In the works of F. Rabelais, N. V. Gogol, Saltykov-Shedrin and Sabir, the negativity caused by life and society is satirized. In Fuzuli's ghazals, the most lyrical and most delicate emotions of the human heart are written, understanding the world with love, illuminating the path to God with love, and gaining attraction are in the center of attention. In the novel, all these can be combined - both dramatic moments, tragic and comic situations. As an example, we can cite the novels of the genius Russian writer F. M. Dostoyevsky. His novels "Humiliation and Insulted People", "The Idiot", "The Gambler", "Crime and Punishment", "The Brothers Karamazov" reflect different aspects of life (tragic, dramatic and comic). For example, in the novel "Crime and Punishment", Dostoyevsky depicted the tragedy of an intelligent young man who was deprived of normal life conditions and was driven to crime due to lack of financial means. This tragedy covers all shades of the human heart, the hero's lifestyle and the environment in which he lives. Smart, thoughtful moments of the hero alternate with intense, complex situations. Another example: let's turn to the novel "Anna Karenina" by the genius Russian writer L.N.Tolstoy. This work is not a description of an ordinary family conflict, but a social novel covering all distances and layers of society. Tolstoy takes the boundaries of this conflict from family to society. Just as she reflects the loving heart of Anna Karenina with all her feelings and excitement, she can also get down to the cold and emotionless heart of her official husband, Karenin. Revealing the whole essence of Karenin's moral philosophy, Tolstoy

summarizes this way of thinking as the way of life of the high nobility of Russia at that time. In "Anna Karenina" syntheticism, which is characteristic of real, realistic novels, alternation of tragic, lyrical and dramatic situations increases the artistic influence and emotionality of the work. We can observe the same situation in the novel "War and Peace". The prominent writer-critic Mehdi Huseyn rightly noted in his article "Writer and History" that: "If the historian reflects the general social relations of the time, the writer mostly analyzes the psychology of the time. A historian is not a psychologist. But the artist must be a psychologist. Although the science of history is created without it, a historical-artistic work cannot be created. ...Modern Soviet historian Academician Tarle very rightly points out that Lev Tolstoy was not interested in diplomatic conversations in the Petersburg salons, but perhaps in the excitement in Natasha Rostova's heart. (4, 417)

A third reason: among all genres of literature, the novel is a genre that reflects the era, time, past and modern life with wide epic plates: studying the history, cultural-ethical level, ethnography, many national characteristics, everyday life, the world of feelings and thoughts of a people, even to explore, first of all, it is necessary to turn to the novel. For example, it is enough to read the novels of Balzac, Hugo, Zolia, and Stendhal to follow the history of France, the traditions, national characteristics, and ethical outlook of the French. Or the novels of Tolstoy, Gogol, Turgenev, and Dostoyevsky will create a clear picture of the life, worldview, and taste of different classes and strata of the Russian people. The novels of the great Kyrgyz writer of the 20th century, Chingiz Aitmatov, also introduce us to the nation to which the writer belongs.

A fourth reason: Compared to other genres of prose, the novel attracts attention by creating full characters. It is possible to create such characters in stories and narratives. However, the characters in the novel cover both the breadth of the boundaries of the description and a short period of time, not a few days or months, but a wider time. The life, feelings and thoughts of the characters in the novel, and their relationships with the surrounding world require a wide description. The main character of the novel should be described so fully that after reading the work you can say: Madame Bovary's novel ("Madame Bovary"), Jean Valjean's novel ("Les Miserables"), Raskolnikov's novel ("Crime and Punishment"), Firudin's novel ("Future day») etc.

Gulu Khalilov, while grouping the sources from which the Azerbaijani novel is nourished, initially turns to folk creativity. According to him, "sometimes an original folklore work, story, poem, fairy tale is created on the basis of an ordinary remark, anecdote and tale, and these, like serious works, show their influence in the formation and organization of other genres. (5, 21-22) He shows that novellas created in Italy in the 14th century played a major role in the development of Italian prose and notes that this experience of Italy was later transferred to France, England, and Spain. The narratives and fairy tales that circulate in the mouths are gradually refined and improved, and based on this, a new genre of fairy tales, stories, etc. arises. Sometimes these novellas are nourished by popular narratives and combined with realistic events, revolve around a person, this characteristic person gradually becomes a hero. For example, Bertoldo in Italian folklore, Pedro Urdemalas in Spanish folklore, and Til Ulenspiegel in German folklore were originated this way. Works of this type are known as "folk novels". (5, 22)

A fifth reason: the novel can be called the philosophy of prose in terms of its mission. Unlike all other genres, in the novel, the essence and understanding of the world itself is drawn into the center of attention. The cruel truths of life, society, and the world are brought to life in the novel. Philosophy, law, psychology, history, sociology ... all these sciences contribute to one degree or another in the literary text of the novel. A novel is an artistic material, and to philosophize on this artistic material, to convey historical truths to the readers in a scientific way, would have reduced the novel to nothing as

an artistic work. The author of the novel revives history not as it is, but through his artistic imagination.

The result

In fiction works, especially in the novel, a strong tendency to psychological analysis, deep penetration into the inner world of the image, spiritual and mental processes taking place in his inner world should also be noted. It is very important to have a psychological context in any novel. By presenting the image not only in the process of action, but also in the psychological plane, the writer can reveal its character in its full meaning. So, it is difficult to imagine the novel without psychological analysis, and this opinion is confirmed by a number of examples of world literature, as well as Azerbaijani prose. Thus, the novel has a number of advantages compared to other literary genres, and we tried to highlight some of them.

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